

Studying the Tensile Properties and Morphology Test for the Self Cured PMMA Resin of Prosthetic Complete Denture.

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ABSTRACT:

In the present search, attempts are made to develop the properties of PMMA resin that used for prosthetic complete denture base material, by addition two different types of particles, which included: nano-hydroxyapatite (nHA) particles and micro-zirconia (ZrO_2) particles that added with different volume fractions of (1, 2 and 3) % to poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA), as cold cured resin. Also woven glass fiber kind (E-glass) and woven Kevlar fiber kind (49), it were added with a fixed volume fraction of 5 % to PMMA composites. In this work the composite prosthetic dentures specimens preparation was done by using (Hand Lay-Up) method as six groups which includes: the first group consists of PMMA resin reinforced by nHA particles, the second group consists of PMMA resin reinforced by ZrO_2 particles, the third group consists of (PMMA-nHA) and glass fiber layer as laminated composite, the fourth group consists of (PMMA- ZrO_2) and glass fiber layer, the fifth group consists of (PMMA-nHA) and Kevlar fiber layer and the sixth group consists of (PMMA- ZrO_2) and Kevlar fiber layer. The experimental part of this work included performing tensile test. In addition, morphology test was done by (SEM). The result of this experimental research shows that the values of tensile strength and modulus of elasticity increased with increasing the volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles for all groups specimens, and all values of elongation decreased with increasing volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles. And the composite prosthetic dentures (PMMA- ZrO_2) show greater values for tensile strength and modulus of elasticity properties. While, the reinforcement by nHA particles had shown greater values for elongation for all groups' specimens. Also the results shown the maximum values for hybrid laminated composite materials for tensile strength and modulus of elasticity properties is obtained in hybrid laminated composite materials for sixth groups' specimens. While the maximum value for elongation is obtained for first groups' specimens.

Key Words: Composite Materials, PMMA, HA Particles, ZrO_2 Particles, Glass Fibers, Kevlar Fibers, Tensile Strength, Modulus of Elasticity, Elongation, SEM.

الخلاصة

تم في هذا البحث إجراء عدة محاولات لغرض تطوير مواصفات راتنج البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت المستخدم لمادة قاعدة طقم أسنان اصطناعي كامل. وقد حضرت هذه المواد المترابكة من البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت كراتنج معالج ذاتياً. وقد تم تقويتها بنوعين مختلفين من الدقائق تضمنت دقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايت النانوية ودقائق الزركونيا الميكروية اضيفت بكسور حجمية مختلفة هي (1، 2 و 3) %، ونوعين مختلفين من الالياف الحصبيرية التثنائية الاتجاه هي الياف الزجاج نوع (E-GLASS) والياف الكفلر نوع (49) وقد اضيفت الى المواد المترابكة

بكسر حجمي ثابت هو (٥ %). هذا البحث حضرت عينات من أطعام الاسنان الأصبغية المتراكبة بطريقة (الصبغ اليدوي) على شكل ستة مجاميع هي: المجموعة الاولى تضم راتنج البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت ودقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايث النانوية، المجموعة الثانية تضم راتنج البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت ودقائق الزركونيا، المجموعة الثالثة تضم راتنج البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت واللياف الزجاج مع دقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايث النانوية، المجموعة الرابعة تضم راتنج البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت واللياف الزجاج مع دقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايث النانوية، المجموعة السادسة تضم راتنج البولي مثيل ميثا اكريليت واللياف الكفلر مع دقائق الزركونيا. يتضمن الجزء العملي من هذا البحث اجراء فحص الشد، بالإضافة الى فحص البنية المجهرية والذي أنجز بواسطة المجهر الإلكتروني الماسح. أظهرت نتائج البحث بان قيم مقاومة الشد ومعامل المرونة ازدادت مع زيادة الكسر الحجمي لدقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايث النانوية ودقائق الزركونيا الميكروية ولكافة مجاميع العينات، وكافة قيم الاستطالة قلت مع زيادة الكسر الحجمي لدقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايث النانوية ودقائق الزركونيا. وان التقوية لأطعام الاسنان الأصبغية المتراكبة بأستخدام دقائق الزركونيا اعطى قيم أعلى لخواص مقاومة الشد ومعامل المرونة، بينما التقوية بأستخدام دقائق الهيدروكسي اباتايث النانوية اعطى قيم أعلى لخاصية الاستطالة ولكافة مجاميع العينات. كذلك أظهرت النتائج بان اعلى قيم للمواد المتراكبة الطباقية الهجينية لخصائص مقاومة الشد ومعامل المرونة ظهرت في المواد المتراكبة الطباقية الهجينية لعينات المجموعة السادسة. بينما اعلى قيمة للاستطالة ظهرت في عينات المجموعة الاولى.

1- INTRODUCTION

Biomaterials are defined as materials natural or synthetic origin that are used as treatment, supplement, or replacing any part of a living tissues or to do function in close contact with living tissue. Therefore two important criteria which biomaterial must fulfill are biocompatibility and bio-functionality (Ramakrishna S. et. al., 2001).

Many biomaterials are available in medicine and dentistry field. The uses of biomaterials include replacement of a body part that has lost function due to disease or trauma, to assist in healing, or to improve function, and to correct abnormalities. Biomaterials can be classified as metals, ceramics, polymers and composites materials. Polymeric materials have a wide variety of applications for implantation since they are available in a wide variety of compositions and properties.

Prosthetic dentistry is the replacement of missing teeth, which may have been lost for a variety of reasons, with either fixed or removable dentures, that using depending upon a many factors of these replacements.

The fracture of acrylic resin denture remains an unresolved problem and failure is probably because a multiplicity of factors rather than the intrinsic properties of the denture base materials and found the stress produced within the denture. The majority of the failure of denture base materials is the fracture, in a survey reported that (63% to 68%) of complete denture prostheses had broken within few years after fabrication. This is caused primarily by impact failure when the denture is accidentally dropped on the hard surface or by fatigue failure when the denture deforms repeatedly through the occlusal forces. This research studying the effected of different type of reinforced materials on the mechanical properties for the composite material, such as (tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, etc), some researches which are accomplished in this field it's:

Schajpal and Sood, (1989), added powdered silver, copper or aluminum (99.9 %) pure with average particle size of 10 μm into PMMA acrylic denture base resin in ratio of (5, 10, 15, 20 and 25) % (5%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 25%) by volume fraction. It was found that all of the metal fillers marginally increased compressive strength, but a decrease in tensile strength resulted as the percentage of filler was increased, silver and copper made the resin more radiopaque, while aluminum did not, the fillers increased thermal conductivity progressively but did not proportionally as the filler concentration increased.

Al-Karagholi, (1992), attempt to produce radiopaque denture base material by adding (1 and 1.5) % by weight Kevlar fiber and (10 and 15) % barium sulphate into acrylic resin material these were polymerized by microwave and water bath curing systems. The comparisons were made on the bases of tensile strength, indentation hardness, modulus of elasticity and radiopacity. From the results of this investigation it was concluded that the

addition of Kevlar fiber causes remarkable improvement in the mechanical properties of the resin. Also it was found that incorporation of both Kevlar fiber and barium sulphat into PMMA produced radiopaque material which retains good mechanical properties.

Vallittu. P.K. et. al., (1995), they investigated the properties of the unidirectional denture glass fiber-poly methyl methacrylate (GF-PMMA) denture composite and compared with the continuous glass fiber or metal wire. The results showed that both types of reinforcement increased the impact strength of PMMA. The study revealed that the concentration of glass fiber greater than (25%) yield better impact strength than steel wire. Also the increased amount of these fibers in the PMMA matrix (up to 14.8% by weight) lead to increased the mean tensile strength of the test specimens from (40.5 MPa) to (91.2 MPa) and the modulus of elasticity from (2057 MPa) to (3751 MPa).

Zeina, (2006), study the effect of reinforced materials on the some of physic- mechanical properties of visible light cured resin (impact and tensile strength, Transverse, surface hardness, water sorption and solubility). The result showed that the addition of glass fibers with (1.5%) improved the impact resistance with (12.7%) and hardness (58%) and had little effect on tensile strength, transverse strength and surface roughness. And Kevlar fibers incorporation with (0.35%) produced obvious reduction in (transverse, impact and tensile strength) with a considerable improvement in hardness about (83%).

Bandugula et. al., (2005), study the nano-composite fabricated by free radical polymerization process for PMMA denture resin and TiO₂. The result indicated that stress intensity values increase as the concentration of titanium oxide increases up to (1%) and subsequently decrease at higher concentration. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of fracture surfaces afforded clues as to the possible deformation mechanism. It was observed that samples opaque as the concentration of TiO₂ was increased beyond (1%) volume fraction.

Chow Wen Shyang et. al., (2012), when surface treatment of HA using zirconate agent (ZCA) carried out to improve the interfacial bonding between the PMMA matrix and HA filler. The effects of different concentration of ZCA on the mechanical properties of PMMA/HA composites was investigated using tensile and flexural tests. The morphological properties of the PMMA/HA composites was characterized by using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). It was found that (PMMA-5% HA-2% ZCA) composites exhibited higher flexural strength compared to that of untreated PMMA/HA composites. This is attributed to the enhancement of interaction between PMMA and HA, which evidenced by FESEM and EDX technique.

The aim of this research is studying the effect of selected volume fractions of (nHA and ZrO₂) particles and (woven glass, woven Kevlar) fibers on the tensile properties of the composite prosthetic complete denture specimens and define the morphology nature of this specimens by SEM test.

2- MATERIALS AND METHODS

2-1 Materials Used

In this research the composite prosthetic dentures specimens consist of polymer matrix and reinforced materials (relatively high stiffness and high wear resistance).

Matrix Material included PMMA cold curing that used in this research as new pour (fluid) resin matrix, type (Castavaria) supplied from (Vertex – Dental Company), to preparation specimen as hybrid and non hybrid laminated composites of the denture prosthetic. Vertex™ Castavaria is a multifunctional self polymerizing acrylic which is perfectly useable as a pouring, relining, rebasing and as a repair acrylic.

This type of materials distinguishes by many properties compared with other type of PMMA polymer such as: softer feel, low molecular weight, color stable in the long run, minimized shrinkage, stable polymerization cycle with a perfect end result, the acrylic is long pourable and modelable for a long period of time. But have low strength, hardness and more difficult using during fabrication (William. J & O' Brain, 2002).

Two types of particles were used in this study as reinforces materials with volume fraction of (1, 2 and 3) % it was added to the polymer powder (acrylic powder) including: the zirconium oxide (ZrO_2) is supplied as partially stabilized particles form, supplied from (ZIRCONIA SALES-GUI 185 SS-U.K Company). The result of particle size distribution of (ZrO_2) particles is obtained by AFM shows the average value of diameter was (112.31 nm).

The HA particles most common widely used in medical application. HA is supplied as a nano-particles form and represented as chemical formula $Ca_5(PO_4)_3OH$ supplied from (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany Company). The result of particle size distribution of (HA) particles is obtained by AFM shows the average value diameter was (69.97 nm).

Two types of fibers were used in this study including: E-glass fiber supplied from (Mowding LTD-U.K Company). And the Kevlar 49 fiber used in this research supplied from (E.I.Dupont de. Nomours Company), as form a woven roving with angle direction ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) and volume fraction (5%) used in this research.

2-2 Preparation Methods of Test Specimens

2-2-1 Mould Preparation

The mould used in this study is made of glass mould with dimensions (20cm × 20cm × 0.4cm) and covered with a glass plate to provide smooth surface of prepared specimens. Thermal silicon was used to close any spaces that may be found in the mould.

2-2-2 Proportioning and Mixing of Acrylic

The Vertex™ Castavaria was used to prepare the specimens of the PMMA composite materials. The standard proportion in mixing ratio is usually for cold cure acrylic resin of (17 g) polymer powder (PMMA) and (10 ml) monomer liquid (MMA) (1.7 g / 1 ml) by volume or (1.7g / 0.95g) by weight according to the manufacturer's instructions of company.

The importance of this ratio was related to control the workability of the mixture, dimensional changes on setting and considered one of the variables influence the cytotoxicity of acrylic resin (Jorge. J. H. et. al., 2003).

When mixing powder and liquid many changes will take place due to the solution of polymer in the monomer. The stages in mixing monomer and polymer acrylic materials include (sandy or granular, sticky, full dough, rubbery and hard). The speed with which the polymer and monomer mixture reaches to dough stage depends upon the solubility of the polymer powder in the monomer liquid and increasing the temperature (Harrison. Z. et. al., 2004).

The Vertex Castavaria is mouldable for a long period of time, where the mixture was mixed of liquid (MMA) in the clean and dry container (glass beaker), follow after that by slow addition of dry powder (PMMA) to liquid (MMA), the mixture was stirred at room temperature continuously by using mechanical mixing (brabender plastograph mixer) at speed (20 r.p.m.) until reached to the dough stage and poured with thin straight line in the center of opening mould with maximum time about (4.5 min) according to manufacture company. During mixture pouring in the glass mould, the mould must be rocked very gently and vibrated from side to side to remove any gas bubbles from the specimens, and reminder of the mixture was poured into mould hole until the glass mould filling. This mixture was covered in closed container and left to stand on the bench top at room temperature (23 ± 2) °C for (8-13) min at beginning of mixing process as working time to increase the viscosity of mixture and surface of pouring become hard and matt.

2-2-3 Curing Cycle Employed

According to the manufacture's instruction polymerization curing the closed mould was placed in the pressure vessels (autoclave). Therefore all specimens were then placed inside autoclave at (55 °C) and pressure equal to (2.5 bar) and let for (30 min), since the specimens' complete polymerization under this condition. The advantage of this technique is polymerization may be accomplished in short time, post cured of specimens and give minimum level of residual monomer.

2-2-4 Cooling Process

After polymerization completion follow by curing process, the mould was allowed to stand outside of the autoclave and put on the bench for cooling time about (30 min) at room temperature to complete the cooling and complete hardening of specimen. After cooling, the specimens was de-mould to remove from the mould carefully and cleaning.

2-2-5 Grinding and Polishing

After a complete cooling of the specimen, all the specimens were finished and polished. All flatter shape access, smooth surface, flashes of acrylic and removed all remaining small scratches with an straight acrylic bur was used followed by the finishing of the specimens was done with the sand paper or silicon carbide grit papers (grades 120-220-320-500) with continuous water cooling. While polishing was accomplished by using fine cloth with diamond paste in grade of (2 µm) or white stiff bristle brush (grade 360).

3- EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

The tensile test is performed according to (ASTM D638-03) by using tensile machine (universal testing machine), type (Instron) at a cross head speed (strain rate) of (5mm/min) and load was applied equal to (5 kN) until break the specimen occur. As recommended by (ADA Specification No.12, 1999). All these tests carried out in air at room temperature (23 ± 2) °C after complete finishing and polishing processes, and immersion the specimens in distilled water at (37 ± 1) °C for (48 hr), in order to remove any residual monomer and release residual stress, also to ensure that the denture base materials remains in semi oral environment. Five specimens where used for most tests and final results represent the average for five specimens it was tested. Morphology test of tensile specimens was done by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique (Annual Book of ANSI/ADA Standard, 1999 and Annual Book of ASTM Standard, 2003).

4- RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4-1 Results and Discussions of Tensile Test for Modified Composites

The tensile strength and modulus of elasticity values results obtained from tensile test that carried out on PMMA composite are illustrated in Figures (1), (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6) respectively. From Figures (1) and (4) can be noticed that the values of tensile strength and modulus of elasticity increased with increasing the volume fraction for both types of particles in the PMMA composite materials. This is due to the strengthening mechanism and nature of bonding, reinforced particles and interface between reinforcing materials and PMMA matrix. Additionally to nature of (nHA and ZrO₂) particles which are harder than PMMA (S. M. Elie., 2007 and Joyce Y. Wong et. al., 2007).

Also can be noticed in these Figures that the values of tensile strength and modulus of elasticity for second group (ZrO₂-PMMA) composite specimens are higher than values their

counter parts of the first group (nHA-PMMA) composite specimens, and increased with a higher rate comparing with the behavior of first group specimens. This improvement in the mechanical properties which associated with the addition of ZrO_2 particles to the polymer PMMA that related to the nature of ZrO_2 particles which are have high hardness and strength comparing with H.A particles. Thus the tensile strength values increased from (52 MPa) for PMMA (as referenced) to (68.5 MPa) for (PMMA-3% ZrO_2) composite. And the modulus of elasticity values increased from (1.65 GPa) for PMMA (as referenced) to (2.252 GPa) for (PMMA-3% ZrO_2) composite.

From the Figures (2), (3), (5) and (6) can be seen that when addition of woven mat of glass fiber or Kevlar fiber in PMMA composite, the tensile strength and modulus of elasticity increased with increasing (nHA and ZrO_2) contact in composites except the modulus of elasticity for the hybrid laminated composite specimens (PMMA-5% G.F or 5% K.F- nHA) as shown in Figure (5) it was slightly decreased with increase these particles. This could be attributed to the fact that glass fiber and Kevlar fibers are characterized by their high tensile strength and resistance to crack propagation compared with PMMA matrix; therefore the hybrid laminated composite specimens can be carried out higher load. But some time the decrease of wettability between matrix (PMMA) and reinforced material (fiberglass, Kevlar fibers and HA) and this lead to decrease cohesive force between reinforcing materials and PMMA matrix, and created many internal defect specially inside fiber this is may be cause decreasing bonding strength between the matrix and the reinforced material.

Furthermore, it can be noticed in these Figures that the values of tensile strength and modulus of elasticity increased with increasing volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles for all hybrid laminated composite specimens, this is due to the contribution of either (nHA or ZrO_2) particles, glass fiber and Kevlar fiber to carried out of the load applied on the hybrid laminated composite specimen with suitable the nature and volume fraction of them. Additionally to regular and randomly distribution of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles inside the PMMA resin and ease penetration the matrix material through the particles and fibers this is lead to create good adhesion at interfaces between the matrix material and reinforcing material, this is lead to an increase in the efficiency of stress transfer from the PMMA composite to the fibers as results an increase in the tensile strength with every increase in volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles (Henning Kaiser, et. al., 2001).

As well as it can be notice in Figures (2), (3), (5) and (6) that the values of tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the hybrid laminated composite specimens reinforced by woven mat Kevlar fiber are higher than those values of the hybrid laminated composite specimens reinforced by woven mat glass fiber with every increase in the volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles, this is due to the characteristics that distinguished the Kevlar fiber which have high tensile strength compared with glass fiber specialization the fibers that carried out the large part of the external stress applied on composite material specimen. Thus the higher values of tensile strength reach to (140.5MPa) for hybrid laminated composites (PMMA-5% Kevlar fiber-3% ZrO_2) as compared to (68.5 MPa) for (PMMA-3% ZrO_2) composite, and the higher values of modulus of elasticity reach to (8.121 GPa) for hybrid laminated composites (PMMA-5% Kevlar fiber-3% ZrO_2). Finally, the percentage improvement of tensile strength was (62.98 %) and the percentage improvement for modulus of elasticity was (79.68 %).

The elongation percentage at break values results obtained from tensile test that carried out on PMMA composite materials and hybrid laminated composite materials for all groups specimen that prepared are shown in Figures (7), (8) and (9) respectively.

From the Figure (7) can be noticed that the values of elongation percentage decreased with increasing the volume fraction of both types of particles with symmetrically manner approximately for both groups of PMMA composite materials. This is because of any increasing in the particle number, it will be act as localized stress concentration regions. Therefore, the elongation percentage will be decreased. Also the decreasing in the elongation percentage depends up on the interfaces bonding between the PMMA matrix and reinforcing

material (nHA and ZrO₂) particles therefore the decreasing in the elongation percentage may be attributed to the formation strong structure of the PMMA composite material for specimen of this groups (Screekanth M. S. et. al., 2009).

Furthermore, it can be noticed in this Figure that the values of elongation percentage for second group (ZrO₂-PMMA) composite specimens are lower than values of elongation percentage for first group (nHA-PMMA) composite specimens. This is due to the higher mechanical strength of ZrO₂ particles comparing with H.A particles.

From the Figures (8) and (9) can be seen that when addition of woven mat of glass fiber or Kevlar fiber in PMMA composite, the elongation percentage decreasing. This could be attributed to the fact that glass fiber and Kevlar fiber are characterized by their higher stiffness compared with PMMA matrix, that lead to increasing the mechanical restraint of PMMA composite, final resulted decreasing in the elongation percentage of the hybrid laminated composite specimens.

Furthermore, it can be noticed in these Figures that the values of elongation percentage decreases with increasing the volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO₂) particles for all hybrid laminated composite specimens. The decreasing in the elongation percentage depends up on the interface bonding between reinforcing materials and PMMA matrix, as well as between different reinforced woven mat of fibers, therefore the decreasing in the elongation percentage may be attributed to the formation strong structure of all hybrid laminated composite specimens (Sawalha S. et. al., 2007).

As well as it can be notice in Figures (8) and (9) that the values of elongation percentage for the hybrid laminated composite specimens reinforced by woven mat glass fiber are higher than values compared with the values of elongation percentage for the hybrid laminated composite specimens reinforced by woven mat Kevlar fiber with every increase in the volume fraction of (nHA and ZrO₂) particles. This is due to the characteristic that distinguished the glass fiber have high elongation percentage at break compared with Kevlar fiber. Thus the elongation percentage value decreased from (5.2 %) for PMMA (as referenced) to lower value (2.55 %) for hybrid laminated composites (PMMA- Kevlar fibers- 3% ZrO₂).

4-2 Results and Discussions of (SEM) Test for Modified Composites

(A) The changes in surface morphology are evaluated for the following prepared specimens:

1. (PMMA-3% Nano-Hydroxyapatite) composite.
2. (PMMA-3% Nano-Hydroxyapatite-5% Glass fiber) composite.
3. (PMMA-3% Nano-Hydroxyapatite-5% Kevlar fiber) composite.
4. (PMMA-3% Micro-Zirconium oxide) composite.
5. (PMMA-3% Micro-Zirconium oxide-5% Glass fiber) composite.
6. (PMMA-3% Micro-Zirconium oxide-5% Kevlar fiber) composite.

(B) Morphological information of a composite after a mechanically induced break of composite with different composition was studied using SEM micrographs for all specimens of polymer composites that mentioned above.

The properties of polymer composites strongly depend on their morphology. This is determined by the particles size, particle size distribution, particles shape, ratio of components, component melt viscosities and processing conditions. In most heterogeneous systems, a morphology where by one phase is distributed in another phase is observed. The matrix phase is typically formed from the larger volume ratio component and at a specific volume ratio, the matrix and reinforced phases are interchangeable (phase inversion), inversion is important since at this ratio the properties of the composite, such as stiffness and impact strength, change in an advantageous manner (F. Ronkay, 2011 and F. Ronkay et. al., 2010).

Furthermore, micro or nano particles and fiber reinforcement of polymer can have different effects on polymer composites. Compatibilization occurs when both components are well-

adhered to the particles. These particles can accumulate in one of the components, and morphological change can occur due to modified component ratio that corresponds to phase inversion (A. Pegoretti, et. al., 2009 and F. Ronkay, 2011).

The effects of (nano-hydroxyapatite and micro-zirconia) particles content on the fracture surface of PMMA composites formerly mention are shown in Figures (10 a, b, c, d, e and f). The SEM micrographs show the difference in the fracture surface morphology which depends on the components composite, the fracture surface morphology of (PMMA- ZrO_2) composites and (PMMA-3% ZrO_2 -5% Glass fiber) in Figures (10 a and c) much smoother fracture surface, which seems to indicate better interfacial adhesion between all components of PMMA composite as compared with fracture surface morphology of the other groups composite specimens that reinforcement with glass fibers, Kevlar fibers and nano-hydroxyapatite. In Figures (10 b, d, e and f), the rough fracture surface of PMMA composites was changed due to the addition of nano-hydroxyapatite, glass fibers and Kevlar fibers to the composite. Furthermore morphological results clearly show that the fracture surface behavior as that displayed ductile behavior since the fracture surface shows amount of strain change after necking region formation. As well as the SEM showed how the (PMMA-nHA) composite having semi-microspheres structure from inserted the fine grained solid in organic matrix (N. W. Elshereksil et. al., 2009 and S. Devikala et. al., 2014).

However, the PMMA composite contraction was found favorable, since this non-rigid behavior avoided the formation of cracks due to the absence of tensile stresses in the matrix. No density gradients of templates were observed in the cross sections analyses by SEM, showing in all cases a homogenous microstructure. Also observations it can be concluded in these composite systems there was a good compatibility between the organic and inorganic components and the nanometer and micrometer sized inorganic particles are well dispersed in the PMMA matrix. In these Figures, it was found that no attributes of craze formation or growth. Instead, there is some of a central mirror zone (smooth zone), sometimes complete with an inclusion that could serve as a failure initiation site, which is surrounded by a fracture region. This change in fracture morphology is indicative of a change in yield phenomenon, implying suppression of craze formation and growth (Benjamin J. Ash. et. al., 2002).

While, the Figures (11 a, b, c, d and e) in higher magnifications of the fracture morphology of PMMA composites specimen equal to (2000 \times) show the individual nano and micro particles sitting in small voids with no connecting polymer. This suggests that dewetting of the particles and fibers from the matrix has occurs either prior to or during the mechanical testing. The voids also appear to be elongated, in a particular direction, hinting at one method of energy dissipation that is taking place in high strain to failure composites (Khalid Saeed and Nasib Khan, 2014).

SEM micrographs in Figures (11 a, b, c, d, e and f) show the fracture surface morphology with higher magnification (2000 \times) for all group composites specimens, different at (1000 \times) magnification that previously mentioned. It is noticed that the crazing form within the fracture surface to indicting the ductile fracture behavior, whereas (nano-hydroxyapatite and micro-zirconia) particles is employed as reinforced material for the blend polymer matrix to restricted the crazes or cracking propagation.

5- CONCLUSIONS

From the presented results of this research, the following can be the conclusions:

- 1- The tensile properties (tensile strength and modulus of elasticity) of PMMA composites (PMMA-nHA), (PMMA- ZrO_2) and hybrid laminated composites specimens, increased with increasing of the volume fractions of (nHA and ZrO_2) particles. While the elongation which was decreased for all types of PMMA composite and hybrid laminated composites specimens.
- 2- The addition of ZrO_2 particles has a noticeable effect on the tensile properties (tensile strength and modulus of elasticity) of PMMA composite prosthetic denture base for all

- groups' specimens more than the HA particles. While, the elongation has higher values when addition HA particles.
- 3- The maximum values for properties (tensile strength and modulus of elasticity) were obtained in hybrid laminated composite materials (PMMA-K.F-ZrO₂).
 - 4- The maximum values for elongation was obtained in the PMMA composite materials (PMMA-nHA).

Fig. 1: Tensile Strength of PMMA Composite Materials as Function of (HA or ZrO₂) Particles (Vol %) in Composite.

Fig. 2: Tensile Strength of Hybrid Laminated Composite Materials as Function of HA Particles (Vol %) in Composite and Type of Woven Fibers.

Fig. 3: Tensile Strength of Hybrid Laminated Composite Materials as Function of ZrO₂ Particles (Vol %) in Composite and Type of Woven Fibers.

Fig. 4: Modulus of Elasticity of PMMA Composite Materials as Function of (H.A or ZrO₂) Particles (Vol %) in Composite.

Fig. 5: Modulus of Elasticity of Hybrid Laminated Composite Materials as Function of HA Particles (Vol %) in Composite and Type of Woven Fibers.

Fig. 6: Modulus of Elasticity of Hybrid Laminated Composite Materials as Function of ZrO₂ Particles (Vol %) in Composite and Type of Woven Fibers.

Fig. 7: Elongation (%) of PMMA Composite Materials as Function of (H.A or ZrO₂) Particles (Vol %) in Composite.

Fig. 8: Elongation (%) of Hybrid Laminated Composite Materials as Function of H.A Particles (Vol %) in Composite and Type of Woven Fibers.

Fig. 9: Elongation (%) of Hybrid Laminated Composite Materials as Function of ZrO₂ Particles (Vol %) in Composite and Type of Woven Fibers.

Fig. 10 a, b, c, d, e and f: SEM Images Showing the Different in the Fracture Morphology between the (PMMA-nHA) and (PMMA-ZrO₂) Composites at Magnification (1000×).

Fig. 11 a, b, c, d, e and f: SEM Images Showing the Different in the Fracture Morphology between the (PMMA-nHA) and (PMMA-ZrO₂) Composites at Magnification (2000×).

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